

Management of Severe Asthenoteratozoospermia with Traditional Medicine: A Case Study

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Abstract

Infertility is a disease of the male or female reproductive system defined by the failure to achieve a pregnancy after 12 months or more of regular unprotected sexual intercourse. Fertility issues may represent a stressful situation to the couple's life with important negative psychosocial effects. Ayurveda as a branch of traditional medicine developed a separate specialty for sexual dysfunction, namely Aphrodisiac Therapy (Vajeekarana Chikitsa). It deals with preservation and augmentation of sexual potency and conception of healthy progeny as well as management of defective semen, spermatogenesis along with treatment of seminal related disorders. Sperm quality is affected by various biological and environmental factors. A male patient was diagnosed with asthenoteratozoospermia, which is a combination of two conditions namely, asthenozoospermia (low sperm motility) and teratozoospermia (abnormal sperm morphology). The study patient was treated with ayurvedic medicine (shaman chikitsa) and panchakarma therapy (shodhana chikitsa) for 5 months. After completing the treatment course a semen analysis was performed and improvement was observed in his abnormal condition. The condition changed from severe asthenoteratozoospermia to normozoospermia and finally his wife had conceived successfully.

Introduction

Infertility is one of the burning issues which affect the couple socially and individually in a negative way. The ability of pregnancy depends on the fertility capabilities of a couple. Infertility, defined as the inability to achieve a pregnancy after 12 months of regular, unprotected intercourse (WHO) [7]. Infertility is not a gender specific problem; it may affect the husband or the wife or both of them together. Along with female infertility, male infertility is also an alarming issue that

needs to be given utmost attention. Asthenoteratozoospermia is frequently reported in men from infertile couples. Asthenozoospermia is a condition associated with low or absence sperm motility and teratozoospermia is a condition of morphological abnormalities that are the main causative factors remains, in the majority of cases. There are unknown variety of factors, life style changes, malnutrition, pollution, genetic abnormalities, serious illness to contribute to its pathogenesis [3] [6]. During natural

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sperm maturation, during epididymal transit of sperm the motility is acquired. Active sperm motility is important to reach to fallopian tubes through vaginal intercourse, and it penetrate the cumulus oophorus and for ensuring the processes of egg fertilization [1]. Due to the morphological abnormalities of the spermatozoa it is unable to penetrate an ovum and fail to ensure the fertilization process (2). Therefore, there is a clear association between sperm motility, morphology and the chance for a natural conception [1]. Ayurveda developed a separate specialty, namely Vajeekarana Chikitsa (Aphrodisiac Therapy). Vajeekarana is one of the important branches of Ayurveda that deals with preservation and amplification of sexual potency of healthy man as well as management of defective semen and lack of spermatogenesis along with abnormal seminal parameters (Shukra dushti) [5]. Acharya Sushruta has also mentioned the word Ksheena Retas, while elaborating definition of Vajikarana Tantra while Dalhana opines Ksheena Retas is moderately low level of Shukra occurring in middle age group due to some etiopathology. Fertility potential of Shukra Dhatu is also affected by disease Ksheena Shukra. These lakshnas can be included under qualitative vitiation of Shukra Dhatu. Hence it can be concluded that in Ksheena Shukra due to consumption of various etiological factors and Dushti of Shukravaha Srotas, Shukra Dhatu production is not up to its mark and ejaculated in low volume. In short, which indicate towards quantitative and qualitative changes of Shukra Dhatu. The doshik involvement in this condition is Vata & Pitta Doshas [4]. As per Ayurvedic treatment guideline, the therapeutic intervention plan was designed for such kind of patient with shodhan chikitsa i.e. panchakarma therapy and followed by shamana chikitsa (Medicinal treatment) for 5 months. Sometime may require intraurethral uttarbasti (IUUB) for this patient as better treatment option. IUUB (Uttarabasti) is introduction of medicated decoction into the bladder through urethra in males. Along with these, diet and lifestyle modifications are also advocated which will not only help in better conception but also in producing healthy offspring [8].

Case Report

A male patient aged 32 years, with marital life of 4 years with complaints of failure to conceive of his wife despite of regular unprotected coitus. He works as chartered accountant in a corporate company. The patient’s wife is 24 years old with no known fertility concerns, she reported regular menstrual cycle and flow and her past medical history was negative for any surgical or medical conditions that might affect her fertility status. The respondent was suggested for a semen analysis and he was diagnosed with asthenoteratozoospermia (AT) which ultimately represents a major cause of failure to conceive. After performing routine physical examination, there was no significant abnormality in external genital area. In ayurvedic classics the case report is considered as Shukradushti (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Semen Analysis Report Before Treatment

As per Ayurvedic treatment guideline, the therapeutic intervention plan was designed for the study patient with shodhan chikitsa i.e. panchakarma especially virechana for consecutive 5 days for each month upto 5 months and followed by shaman chikitsa (Medicinal treatment) for 5 months.

Table 1: Therapeutic Intervention

Sl.	Drugs/Therapy	Dose	Anupana	Duration
1	Virechana 1gm	2 tablet daily at night for 5 days per month	Luke Warm Water	3 month
2	Mucuna + Shatavari + Ashwagandha combination	3 tea spoon powder for twice daily	Luke Warm Milk	4 month
3	Ubidecarenone 100 mg	One tablet twice daily	With normal water	4 month
4	Tribulus terrestris	2 tea spoon powder once daily	Luke Warm Milk	4 month
5	Yohimbine 5.4 mg	One tablet daily	With normal water	3 month

Abhyanga (massage therapy) was done with sesame oil along with 5 days Virechana (Therapeutic purgation) for each month. The patient effectively took his panchakarma therapy and mentioned medicine as per treatment plan. After taking 4 month of treatment he performed semen analysis. (Table 1)

Result

The treatment approach based on ayurvedic principles can produce encouraging results in the management of male infertility by improving the quality and quantity of sperm.

Table 2: Comparing Parameters Before and After Treatment by Semen Analysis

SL. No.	Seminal Parameters	Before Treatment	After 4 month of treatment
1.	Collective Procedure	Masturbation	Masturbation
2.	Quantity	1.5 ml	3 ml
3.	Color	Whitish	Whitish
4.	Reaction	Alkaline	Alkaline
5.	Total sperm count	40 million/ml	35 million/ml
6.	Morphology	01% are with normal and 99% abnormal morphology	65% are with normal morphology
7.	Motility	Actively Motile: 01%	Actively Motile: 30%
		Sluggishly motile: 00%	Sluggishly motile: 40%
		Non motile: 99% (Dead)	Non motile: 30%
8.	Pus cell	4-6/HPE	2-4/HPE
9.	Epithelial Cell	0-2/HPE	0-2/HPE
10.	Comments	Severe asthenoteratozoospermia	Normozoospermia

Figure 2: Semen Analysis Report After Treatment

After completion of the 4 months of treatment in follow-up to assess the improvement status of the patient, semen analysis was performed on 5th November 2022. The report revealed that the seminal parameter were improved significantly from asthenoteratozoospermia to normozoospermia e.g. sperm actively motility increases from 01% to 30%, sluggish motility increase from 0% to 40%, non-motility decreases from 99% to 30%. Apart from the morphological parameter of sperm was improved from 01% to 65% considerably [Fig-2].

Lifestyle modification (Nidanparivarjana)

Along with all of these medications it is very important to follow healthy lifestyle and avoid unhealthy diet (ahara) which are antagonistic to the production of

sperm (shukra). Patient was advised to include more nuts, beans, citrus fruits, green leafy vegetables in his diet. He was also advised to restrict the use of bike riding, avoid tight clothing. The patient completely avoided smoking and alcohol which added to the positive outcome [3].

Conclusion

Nowadays male infertility is one of the most common disorders in OPD or Clinics. It has substantial economic impact on health care cost. This Ayurvedic treatment guideline including the combination of both shodana and shaman therapies were helpful to improve the abnormal seminal parameters to a satisfactory level. After completed 4 months of treatment and maintained proper lifestyle, the study patient was improved the seminal parameters from severe asthenoteratozoospermia to normozoospermia. Hence the mentioned treatment approach was effective and gave optimal results. This case study suggests that there is a wider scope for the better management of male infertility especially severe asthenoteratozoospermia and offers potential research area in the department of sexual invigorations (vajikaranachikitsa) of Ayurvedic medicine.

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